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JUMPING SKILLS OF VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ACTION GAMES IN FORMATION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the development of soccer skills of young volleyball players with the help of action games is highlighted.

Active games wide comprehensive and bright national values to the series belongs to its own essence and content in terms of humanity of development certain stages special social-economic, cultural domestic, spiritual educational in the circumstances different people and people by invention done. This of games evolutionary and ethnogenetic basically strict look to them has been interest more and more increased is going Especially our country independent development during mobile games recovery from them health, physical and psychological perfection as use issues state attention focused is coming. Sports games volleyball sports in type too young generation healthy and physically perfect to do educate important to the point have being is coming This about initial from stages volleyball sports in type of athletes, bravery ability development (vertical jump, diagonal jump to the side and back jump, jump speed, jump endurance) qualities simple standard physical exercises, weights (arms and legs and to the waist connectable lead plates), fixtures and trainers using fast development can. But first preparation and study - exercise in groups take to go in training sacrosanct qualities such approach based on development young the children straining to put inevitable, first of all there is them such exercises fast exhausts interest - fades, children only jump about they think That's why for sacrosanct qualities in development to himself special special mobile games, playful from relays use to the goal is appropriate. Young in children sacrosanct qualities mobile games using development advantage attention play by pointing exercises how jump skill development that it is necessary looking choose necessary that emphasizes. For example, obviously to land development need "parachutists", one of time in itself one group children sacredness game "hook" in development exercise recommendation is enough To the length jump

- from each other away drawn to the characters jump game through development possible it is "Who higher", "who longer", "who more precisely" jump exercises too these are including

Physical adjectives to develop directed game exercises, maybe jump quality types to form designed, single, in pairs group being and the team in order executable movement games content and essence open gave. High, diagonal, long, side, back, jump skill formative from many - many exercises importance open gave. Especially their "From Obstacles increased transition", "From dong - to dong jump", "Kangaroos", "Rope with jump", "Belt over jump", to the feet bag wearing different the games to play like mobile games sacrosanct and jump endurance qualities in development very hand will come. The game right choose and to the goal according to in the transfer very important important have. But game everyone time who educational tasks solution can't do it. Education in the field good to the result reach for mobile games educational in the spirit organize to be done and content and rules with detailed familiarity, high pedagogical to skill have to be it is necessary. To that he mobile from the games intended education and educational to goals reach takes. Children game during own character and personal features demonstration they do. From this while teacher their different habits, negative and positive actions knowing

get, belong events define the game certain direction put in them honesty, bravery, friendship qualities in the team own duty feeling to do bring up can. That's it with together, he to the children game the rules not broken without creative initiative in showing each in terms of help gives.

Teacher the games transfer in the process didactic of the principles use and always them done to increase reach it is necessary. Teacher to the students each one of the game content, task and the rules explaining gives. This while to them to the game conscious in relation to be, him right by learning get, own mistakes and achievements right to understand and own actions of his comrades to his actions in comparison analysis to do enable gives. Teacher children with held games one little certain difficulties overcome with depends game to be in the process executable each one task done to increase reach and barriers how conquest to be done according to complicating it going necessary. This work teaches children to be hardworking, and their will power increases. In short, the teacher, while preparing for the game, defines its specific tasks, these tasks should be suitable for the children's age, that is, they should be able to perform them. It is very important to encourage students to take the initiative and actively participate in the organization and conduct of the game.

References:

1. Ayrapetyans L.R., Pulatov A.A., Isroilov Sh.Kh. Volleyball // Study guide for high school students. T.: 2009. - 77 p.
2. Kurbanova M.A., Kosimova M.U. National and mobile games. // Study guide for students of higher educational institutions. 2017.- 485 p.